

European Genomic Data Infrastructure

Structure and Organisation

Milestone	MS10: Governance structure, including operational, security, and development committees defined
Authors	Dylan Spalding (CSC), Susanna Repo (CSC), Tommi Nyrönen (CSC)
Contributors	Markus Englund (UU), Mallory Freeberg (EMBL-EBI), Liis Lemsalu (UTARTU), Regina Becker (PNED)
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Introduction

The Genomic Data Infrastructure¹ (GDI) project is a Digital Europe project that aims to deploy a federated infrastructure providing access to genomic and phenotypic data in line with FAIR² (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles to respond to the ambitions of the European 1+ Million Genomes initiative (1+MG)³. The federated European Genomic Data Infrastructure comprises a set of national nodes each of which hosts a subset of the data available within the 1+MG infrastructure. In addition to the national nodes there is a User Portal that provides a single point for data discovery, data access requests, and information about the 1+MG datasets. One of the objectives of the GDI project is to determine a sustainability model on how to operate, maintain, and evolve the data infrastructure services after the GDI project ends in 2026, in collaboration with Pillar I.

Vision for the scope of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure is based on the 1+MG Declaration of signatory countries. Managing the whole genome sequences of 1+ million individuals requires a data infrastructure capable of storing PBs for data with suitable backup (for example distributed replication) connected to high-performance computing, as well as access management and data discovery services. The 1+MG data infrastructure deployed in GDI will be distributed. This means that the logical dataset will exist in geographically connected nodes with appropriate secure network connectivity. The management of the foreseen data infrastructure operations work in close alignment with the 1+MG data governance framework and committees.

¹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

During the GDI project a subset of nodes, termed vanguard nodes, will become operational supporting the five functionalities of data discovery, access management, storage and interfaces, data reception, and processing (or data analysis). This document describes the structure and organisation of the data services needed during the GDI project to ensure the nodes can progress through from onboarding to deployment.

Committee Overview

The structure and organisation of the data services needed for GDI is comprised of four committees:

Table 1: Outline of the four permanent committees.

Committee / Groups	Description	Comments
Management Board	Defines the strategic roadmap GDI to ensure the successful deployment of the GDI services	During GDI this will be the project management board, but will need to evolve after GDI finishes to become an interface towards the 1+MG and Pillar I.
Operations Committee	Monitors operations and coordinates technical roadmaps of the nodes participating in the GDI	Links to Pillar II, primarily WPs 3 and 4.
Outreach and Training Committee	Provides outreach, training, and onboarding documentation, and workshop coordination as well as interfaces with external stakeholders, such as EHDS, in the project etc.	Links to WP5 and Pillar III, but is distinct from the helpdesk, which itself is part of WP4.
Security and Data Protection Committee	Monitors the security and data protection requirements and performance of the network, as well as new developments and threats.	Links to WG2 in 1+MG and Pillar 2. Includes also country ELSI experts. Includes breach response, bad actors, etc.

Committees are permanent during the GDI project, and meet on a self-determined schedule during the duration of the GDI. Action points are always translated into issues tracked on

management software, accessible to all partner members for comments, feedback, or questions. Status updates do not require meetings but must be regularly documented and shared via mailing lists or Slack.

Roles for each committee are clarified below, and a list of contacts is available on a shared portal.

Working groups are temporary groups that are set up to achieve a specific task, such as defining a new Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for extended functionality or an updated Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) template. The working group will be convened and report to one or more committees but allow a focussed task to be performed.

Terms of Reference

1 Management Board

1.1 Purpose

The Management Board responsibilities are defined in the GDI handbook⁴ and will be operational for the duration of the project. Communication will be maintained between the management Board and the Operations, Outreach and training, and Security and Data Protection Committees, though during the project feedback from these committees will be via the appropriate WP or Pillar as defined in the table above. However there will be a requirement to supersede the Management Board to ensure the long-term sustainability of the 1+MG infrastructure post project completion, and this will be defined during the project by Pillar I and the 1+MG Coordination Group.

⁴ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Yeehpl0fZmm9bF58AcDDyXOaXS71NIVrDgMeyf9l4GE/edit#heading=h.oll2ugd3oh1>

Figure 1: Relationship between the Management Board and committees.

2 Operations Committee

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of the Operations Committee is to maintain the GDI infrastructure, coordinate deployment of new and updated services, and facilitate the implementation of technical roadmaps across the GDI nodes to ensure that KPIs, ELSI and GDPR, and customer and stakeholder requirements are met at a European level. National level operations are not in scope, except where these affect European level operations.

Responsibilities include:

1. Monitoring of the KPIs and taking appropriate action to ensure these are met, and periodically reviewing the KPIs to ensure they remain fit for purpose.
2. Establish, maintain and update SOPs across the GDI infrastructure to meet current best practice and ensure customer experience is uniform across the network.
3. Determine areas of improvement or where service levels are dropping and follow appropriate mechanisms to ensure these are addressed, such as setting up working groups.
4. Coordinate the updating, upgrading, or patching of node services to ensure that downtime, both at node and European level, is minimised.
5. Promptly act on actions required by the Security Committee or when necessary to ensure data protection legislation, such as GDPR, is complied with.

6. Provide reports on the performance of the GDI infrastructure to the Management Board as required.
7. Coordinate, track, and address helpdesk issues across the GDI infrastructure.

To enable these responsibilities to be performed the committee will create, maintain, adapt, or replace

1. Compliance Test Suite (in collaboration with the Security Committee)
2. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)
3. Risk Register (in collaboration with the Security Committee and Management Board)
4. Maturity Level Model and TRL definitions (in collaboration with the Management Board)

2.2 Membership

Each operational node must nominate a member to the committee, and a maximum of two members per node is allowed. The committee will also have at least two representatives from the operators and maintainers of the User Portal. Members of any other committee, node, or working group within the GDI will be able to attend as observers.

2.3 Meetings

The committee will agree Rules of Procedure for meetings which will include items such as the decision making process, preparing and sharing of the agenda, minute taking and approval, meeting scheduling and location (in person, hybrid, virtual), and resolution procedures for conflicting node level requirements.

3 Outreach and Training Committee

3.1 Purpose

The purpose of the Outreach and Training Committee is to engage with citizens, other data spaces such as European Health Data Space (EHDS⁵), data users and generators, disease domain use cases (for example 1+MG working groups 8 to 12), industry, and healthcare providers. During GDI this will include Pillar III and WP1. The committee will define, maintain, and update the documentation and outreach materials such as questionnaires and videos, as well as European level GDI outreach events ensuring that these are coordinated across the nodes within GDI, but national level outreach events are out of scope of this committee.

⁵ https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en

Responsibilities include:

1. Generate, maintain, and update public documentation and outreach materials explaining the purpose of GDI
2. Support the operations committee in generating usage statistics and presenting KPIs to stakeholders and the wider public
3. Coordinate representation of GDI at external events between the nodes to ensure a consistent and unified message for European level interactions
4. Identify and engage with new stakeholders to support the expansion and sustainability of GDI across Europe, and the interoperability of GDI outside Europe

3.2 Membership

Each operational node should nominate at least one member for the outreach and training committee, with a maximum of two members. The User Portal operators and maintainers should also nominate at least one member. Members of other committees or working groups can act as observers.

3.3 Meetings

The committee will agree Rules of Procedure for meetings which will include determining the decision making process, preparing and sharing of the agenda, minute taking and approval, meeting scheduling and location (in person, hybrid, virtual), and resolution procedures for conflicting node level requirements.

4 Security and Data Protection Committee

4.1 Purpose

The committee will ensure that the GDI infrastructure conforms to Ethical, Legal, and Societal Issues (ELSI) both at a national and European level. It will take the recommendations from the 1+MG WG2 working group, and ensure that the current infrastructure and operational processes conform to these recommendations as they evolve. Changes to standards or products used within the GDI infrastructure will have to be checked by the security committee. The committee will also oversee the Breach response protocol, and includes members of the Computer Security Incident Response Team (CSIRT) which will respond or coordinate responses to security incidents that involve more than one node or GDI specific operations.

Responsibilities include:

1. Creating, maintaining, and updating incident response plans
2. Maintain and communicate security information to relevant nodes and external stakeholders
3. Coordinate and communicate response efforts
4. Define and maintain SOPs for the detection, assessment and analysis of incidents across the GDI
5. Report incidents to the relevant authorities, standards organisations, or product owners. Create, update, review or deprecate response protocols or security policies based on these reports.
6. Log all incidents and audits, and any actions taken in response
7. Coordinate audits across the GDI to ensure ELSI compliance

Products the Security committee is responsible for include:

1. Incident response protocol
2. Compliance Test Suite (with the Operations Committee)
3. Security procedures and policies
4. Risk Register (with the Operations Committee and Management Board)
5. Incident, product and standard compliance checks, and Audit log

4.2 Membership

Each node should nominate at least one member for the Security Committee, with a maximum of two members. The User Portal operators and maintainers should also nominate at least one member. Members of other committees or working groups can act as observers. Members of the 1+MG WG2 group may also be members.

4.3 Meetings

The committee will agree Rules of Procedure for meetings which will include (but are not limited to) determining the decision making process, preparing and sharing of the agenda, minute taking and approval, meeting scheduling and location (in person, hybrid, virtual), and resolution procedures for conflicting node level requirements.